

DARIAH-ERIC: ANNUAL REPORT 2016

Foreword	5
DARIAH as Research Intelligence	5
What Is DARIAH?	6
Introduction to the DARIAH Annual Report 2016.....	7
Sustainable growth: Members and Cooperating Partners	8
In focus: 2016's new partners.....	8
17 Members and 12 Cooperating Partners in 2016.....	9
List of Members in 2016.....	10
List of Cooperating Partners in 2016	10
New Horizons in Research: VCCs and Working Groups	11
Overview	11
Working Group Snapshots.....	13
WG Impact factors and success criteria (VCC4).....	13
WG Training and Education (VCC2)	14
WG Sustainable Publishing of (Meta)data (VCC3).....	14
Working together: Projects, Partnerships and Outreach.....	15
DARIAH Projects	15
The Humanities at Scale Project.....	15
A first HaS Event: DARIAH Winter School in Prague	15
DESIR	16
Affiliated projects	17
DARIAH Outreach	21
Promoting Research in Europe: An Inter-ERIC Communications Initiative.....	21
Making research accessible: The DARIAH Theme 2016, "Public Humanities"	21
Towards a scientific conference: The first DARIAH Annual Event.....	22

Who's who in DARIAH and who's new?	23
Organisational overview	23
New Board members.....	23
Jennifer Edmond	24
Frank Fischer	25
National Coordinators Committee (NCC)	26
Senior Management Team (SMT).....	26
Dariah Coordination Office (DCO)	26
Virtual Competence Centers (VCC).....	27
New Working Groups	28
Defining Cloud Infrastructure Services for DH.....	28
WG FIM4D (Federated Identity Management for DARIAH).....	28
WG CENDARI Sustain.....	28
WG Women Writers in History (WWIH)	28
WG Sustainable Publishing of (Meta)data.....	28
Administrative, legal and regulatory	29
Budget	29
Income and Expenditures.....	29
External Funding in 2016.....	29
DESIR	29
Project Europeana.....	29
Annexes	30
Annex 1: Report of NCC Activities	30
Annex 2: Report of Joint Research Committee and CIO-Team Activities.....	32
Annex 3: List of National Representatives in 2016	33
Annex 4: List of National Coordinators in 2016	34
Annex 5: List of DARIAH related publications.....	35

DARIAH as Research Intelligence

DARIAH is a devolved, open and multi-layered network, constructed as a Research Infrastructure, or, RI. But “RI” here could also signify “Research Intelligence”. If so, how would we begin to measure such a quotient? What would its formal components and purpose be? In 2016, there were again headlines about the potential danger of “AI”, or Artificial Intelligence, and how advances in this area will represent the greatest existential challenge to the human condition. But interestingly, the necessity of AI was also recognised, as well as its optimal environment.

By some calculations, the Humanities have been going digital for nearly 70 years. We as digitally-enabled humanists therefore not only have an embedded place in tertiary education but also possess, to paraphrase Elon Musk, tertiary digital research selves. These take the form not only of the commonplace, such as email, but also syntax trees, visualisations, vocabularies, annotations, as well as spectrographic analyses of cultural objects. This material is vast, multifarious and often located remotely. The application of our natural intelligence and reflexive curiosity as humanists creates a huge amount of machine-based intelligence. What is missing to connect the two?

DARIAH is the research intelligence, the effective bandwidth or network between these two necessary modes of knowledge production in the digitally-enabled humanities. The research intelligence we foster comprises active communities of research

practice (for example, in the form of new working groups this year, covering everything from cloud infrastructure to historical women writers networks) as well as new national partnerships thanks to our cooperating partner programme and six new candidate membership countries in the H2020-funded DESIR project.

A particular aspect of a further H2020-funded project, Humanities at Scale (HaS) looked at how we can do research in a more intelligent and open way: The HaS Prague Winter School brought together an international set of researchers at different levels and experts in publishing to consider Open Science and its application to scholarly publication – from data citation to overlay and data journals, so that what we do as Humanists is also increasingly transparent and democratic.

For the digital is the best possible facilitator in the end for this openness to innovation, new ideas, and novel cooperation across disciplines. It is in this optimal spirit of democracy that DARIAH’s research intelligence is flourishing.

Jacques Dubucs
Chair, DARIAH General Assembly

Laurent Romary
President, DARIAH Board of Directors

What Is DARIAH?

DARIAH is a network, first put on the ESFRI Roadmap in 2006, which connects several hundreds of arts and humanities scholars and dozens of research facilities in 17 European countries, the DARIAH member countries. Additionally DARIAH has cooperating partner institutions in countries that are not members of DARIAH, and strong ties to many research projects across Europe. DARIAH supports digitally-enabled research in the arts and humanities, as well as the teaching of digital research methods. People in DARIAH provide digital tools and share data as well as know-how. They organize learning opportunities for digital research methods, like workshops and summer schools, and offer training materials for Digital Humanities.

Additionally the DARIAH community cooperates in working groups, guided by four thematic Virtual Competency Centres (VCCs), with subjects ranging from the assessment of digital tools to the development of standards and ensuring the long term accessibility of research materials. Their activities may vary but they all share one common goal: providing services to scholars in the arts and humanities and therefore helping them to do innovative research at the forefront of their disciplines.

In 2016, we experienced a great deal of growth and activity across all areas, which are reflected in detail in the report below. Propelled by this and by our formally becoming a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) in late 2014, our steady and exemplary development since then has brought us the significant status this year of being declared a Landmark on the ESFRI Roadmap.

The themes of growth, expansion and embeddedness are therefore prominent in the highlights in the following report: from refining our internal organisation and strengthening our four Virtual Competency Centres (e-Infrastructures, Research and Education Liaison, Scholarly Content Management, and Advocacy, Impact and Outreach), to bringing into DARIAH new interest from the community via working groups and Cooperating Partners, this has been an effective year of consolidation for the network.

This sense of embedded expansiveness has also been exemplified by our leading two major H2020-funded projects, Humanities at Scale (HaS), whose aim is to bring new digital research methods, practices and tools to the awareness of arts and humanities scholars, and DESIR, which is about reaching out to the international DH community, showcasing the strength of European research in the Digital Humanities, as well as ensuring we are a diverse and open community of practice by addressing the particular needs of unaffiliated, women and early career researchers (ECRs).

Our openness as a network this year has been further underlined by our collaborations with other European projects and initiatives – exploring new research techniques, promoting new technologies as well as securing new standards, whether these be technical or benchmarks for training either scholars or those who manage research infrastructures, all of which can be seen exemplified in the section ‘Working together’. It was also made evident in the way in which we made our yearly meeting more outward looking and sponsored a further round of the DARIAH Theme, this year, “Public Humanities”, to promote access to the DARIAH network by non-members as well as providing our Members with the opportunity to speak to and engage with a broader audience, thus also making their work better known. These aspects of our work can be followed in the DARIAH Outreach section.

DARIAH is a large organisation, powered not only by our researcher communities but also by a series of dedicated committees, the DARIAH Coordination Office and the expertise, strategic and academic, on our Board of Directors – information on the central and thematic leadership of DARIAH is available under a comprehensive ‘Who’s who’.

It has been a pleasure to be in such a privileged position, witnessing the growth, confidence and maturity of our endeavours over the past year. I hope you will be as inspired and as motivated by this as I have been.

Mike Mertens, CEO

The DARIAH ERIC is steadily growing. According to its statutes there are three ways of joining the consortium: Countries and intergovernmental organisations can become Observers or Members. Individual institutions from countries, that are not yet DARIAH Observers nor Members, are free to apply for Cooperating Partner Status. A total of six institutions applied and successfully joined the DARIAH network as Cooperating Partners in 2016.

During its virtual meeting in May 2016 DARIAH's General Assembly (GA) accepted applications from Linnaeus University in Sweden, and the UK universities of Swansea and Glasgow as well as from King's College London.

In November 2016, GA members gathered in Vienna also cleared the way for further European cooperation. This time the applicants were Helsinki's Aalto University and the Norwegian University of Science and Technology in Trondheim. "We were very happy about the applications", said DARIAH's Director Laurent Romary after the GA meeting in Vienna. "DARIAH strives to involve the Nordic countries even more. Hence, it is a great success for us to involve the two universities in our work, both are outstanding partners with a great deal of expertise and large versatile networks".

In focus: 2016's new partners

Aalto University is the second largest university in Finland. It consists of four technical schools, the School of Arts and Design, and the School of Business. In the field of Cultural Heritage and Digital Humanities, the university has collaborated with many other Finnish universities as well as cultural heritage organisations. Collaborations with the University of Helsinki have been especially deep and Aalto University participates in the new DH centre HELDIG, the Helsinki Centre for Digital Humanities. Aalto University is well-known internationally for its work on Linked Data technologies, analysing complex network systems, and data mining and learning.

NTNU is Norway's largest university with about 38 000 students. More than 300 PhD- degrees are awarded yearly, within the fields of technology, science, arts and humanities, social sciences and medicine. NTNU has a broad range of contacts within industry, business and the public sector, as well as within art and culture. In order to build up NTNU's research profile in Digital Humanities, the

Art and Technology task force (ARTEC) was founded in March 2015

LNU is one of Sweden's newest higher education institutions. It was formed in 2010 when the University of Kalmar and Växjö University merged, and has today become the sixth largest university in Sweden with 31,000 students in 150 degree programs and 2,500 single-subject courses.

Swansea University offers about 330 undergraduate courses and 120 post-graduate courses to 16,020 students. In its Centre for Excellence on Digital Humanities (CODAH) researchers from many different disciplines come together to work with a wide range of partners and national projects such as CHERISH-DE.

Glasgow University has more than 25,000 undergraduate and postgraduate students from more than 140 countries worldwide. It is a member of the prestigious Russell Group of leading UK research universities, and a founder member of Universitas

21, an international grouping of universities dedicated to setting worldwide standards for higher education.

King's College London is a public research university. King's has over 27,600 students (including

nearly 10,500 postgraduates) from 150 countries and almost 6,800 employees. The university has a distinguished reputation in the humanities, law, the sciences, including health areas such as psychiatry, medicine, nursing and dentistry and social sciences, including international affairs.

17 Members and 12 Cooperating Partners in 2016

In 2016 DARIAH had 17 Member Countries, and no Observers. DARIAH Members create national consortia of research institutions and road maps of national DARIAH activities aimed at advancing Digital Arts and Humanities in the respective country. A National Coordinator hosted by a National Coordinating Institution oversees these activities.

Cooperating Partners can access DARIAH resources and participate in the consortium's activities. They, in return, contribute to shape DARIAH EU through working groups, in which they can showcase their work and offer their own expertise within the extensive network of international digital humanities scholars that DARIAH represents. Although Cooperating Partners have the same access to DARIAH resources as Members and Observers, they cannot determine policy or be represented in the General Assembly, DARIAH's governing and executive body.

By the end of 2016 DARIAH had established ties with a total number of 12 Cooperating Partners from five countries. All of them possess leading expertise in various fields of Digital Humanities. Being able to integrate and make use of this expertise in DARIAH is a win-win situation. The whole network profits from the input of its new partners and the partners benefit from their access to DARIAH's resources. This reciprocity ensures a steadily advancing exchange of scholarly expertise, digital tools and know-how, and, in turn, contributes vastly to furthering and advancing digital research all over Europe.

Apart from the six new Cooperating Partners added in 2016, this branch of the network also includes one university in Sweden, as well as five universities and one research facility in Switzerland.

List of Members in 2016

Member Country	Coordinating Institution	National Coordinator
Austria	Austrian Academy of Sciences	Charly Moerth
Belgium	University of Ghent	Christophe Verbruggen
Croatia	Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research	Koraljka Kuzman Slogar
Cyprus	Cyprus University of Technology	Marinos Ioannides
Denmark	DIGHUMLAB	Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard
France	Huma-Num (CNRS)	Olivier Baude
Germany	University of Göttingen	Heike Neuroth
Greece	Academy of Athens	Helen Katsiadakis
Ireland	National University of Ireland Maynooth	Susan Schreibman
Italy	National Research Council of Italy	Emiliano Degl'Innocenti
Luxembourg	Centre for Contemporary and Digital History	Andreas Fickers
Malta	Malta Libraries Council	Milena Dobрева
Netherlands	International Institute of Social History	Henk Wals
Poland	University of Warsaw	Jakub Szprot
Portugal	Infrastructure ROSSIO	Amélia Aguiar de Andrade
Serbia	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities	Toma Tasovac
Slovenia	Institute of Contemporary History	Jurij Hadalin

List of Cooperating Partners in 2016

COUNTRY	INSTITUTION	REPRESENTATIVE
Finland	Aalto University	Eero Hyvönen (Department of Computer Science)
Norway	Norwegian University of Science and Technology	Thomas Sørli Hansen (Faculty of Humanities)
Sweden	Linnaeus University	Koraljka Golub (Department of Library and Information Science)
Switzerland	University of Basel	Lukas Rosenthaler (Department of Media Studies)
	University of Bern	Michael Stolz (Faculty of German Studies)
	University of Geneva	Laure Ognois (Director of Research Service)
	University of Lausanne	Michael Piotrowski (Faculty of Humanities)
	University of Zurich	Martin Volk (Institute of Computer Linguistics)
	Swiss Academy of Humanities and Social Sciences	Beat Immenhauser (Vice General Secretary of SAHSS)
United Kingdom	Glasgow University	Lorna Hughes (Chair in Digital Humanities)
	King's College London	Sheila Anderson (Faculty of Arts and Humanities)
	Swansea University	Stephen Williams (University Librarian)

Overview

In 2016, the Virtual Competence Centres (VCCs) were further strengthened as reference and contact point for the working groups that they oversee, not only for organisational reasons but also and foremost to leverage their contribution as content specialists in the aspects of infrastructural support they represent (e.g. VCC1 for e-Infrastructures; VCC2 for Research and Education Liaison; VCC3 for Scholarly Content Management and VCC4 for Advocacy, Impact and Outreach).

During 2016 the oversight body of the VCCs, the Joint Research Committee (JRC) with the help of the Chief Integration Officer (CIO) instituted measures to optimize the organizational and operational strategy for all VCCs and for their interaction with the WGs. VCC2 heads (former and sitting) were particularly active in this process and regularly engaged with their constituent WG heads to facilitate the sharing of information and ideas between the CIO team and the WGs. This process was particularly facilitated during the DH2016 meeting in Krakow: the European location of the meeting enabled a number of Working Groups to hold meetings of their members: in particular the Natural Language Processing and Education and Training WGs hosted useful gatherings. Some VCCs are larger than others (see Table WG's and VCC's below), a natural result of the organic, self-determined nature of the WGs, which the JRC has decided to not to steer or alter in any directive way. In response, however, the JRC has adopted a coordinator-expert model (instead of a set of rather distinct subunits) as envisioned by former CIO Henk Harmsen in 2015. In practice, the coordinating VCC is responsible for evaluating new WGs and monitoring their work and mutual collaboration, but with the understanding that any other VCC (Head) can be recruited to contribute to aspects of the WG's activities that may cross VCC expertise areas. This new organizational concept for the VCCs will strengthen the JRC and harness the synergies between DARIAH's communities and its WGs.

The Working Groups in DARIAH self-organise to prepare an application for WG status, and are approved after a thorough review process. Working Group applications signal to DARIAH which topics are currently most urgent or interesting for the communities in the different countries. The fact that DARIAH continues to see the emergence of new WGs is a sign of continuing interest in collaborating and co-shaping the research infrastructure. Already now, the Working Groups have proven to be useful pools from which to draw experts represent DARIAH in meetings, workshops, or European funded projects. The challenge for the next years is to further enhance the collaboration between the Working Groups and to align their work to the strategic direction of DARIAH as a whole. This alignment will contribute to the definition of improved models for sustaining services co-created in cross-collaboration with DARIAH and improved coordination across the organisations many contributory bodies. The new internal funding mechanism (see the organisational overview for details) and special Knowledge Exchange meetings at Annual Events among WG Chairs are two instruments to promote this kind of development.

VCC Heads also strengthen their ability to support integration throughout the DARIAH network through interaction with DARIAH's externally funded projects (see Highlights from WGs). For example, the VCC2 Heads met with representatives of the PARTHENOS project, to share information particularly about training and education. In addition, in the last year the HaS project (Humanities at Scale) played a very central connecting role, involving the CIO, VCC Heads and Working Groups when discussing classification of DARIAH contributions and their assessment criteria (in particular at a meeting in Goettingen in 2016). The CIO team and VCC heads have been involved in the design of an online tool that supports the collection of the National members' in-kind contributions so they can be formally accepted and disseminated to the community. This system will become a core part of the 'marketplace' that DARIAH is developing. Not only is this project

is redefining the ingestion and assessment process, but it investigates the core meaning of the in-kind contributions and redefines them as evolving research outputs that researchers will be able to reuse and share.

We are also hoping to increase the number of specific target-focused meetings between JRC, VCC, WG members and DARIAH projects. COST Actions (including those directly associated with DARIAH as well as others relevant for the Digital Humanities) are also a good platform to disseminate DARIAH. One such example was the COST Action TD1210 KnoweScape (chair Andrea Scharnhorst, CIO) which provided an opportunity to launch the DARIAH membership of Malta, support ShortTermScientificMissions from and to Malta, and to co-organise workshops (<http://knowescape.org/?s=malta+>).

All VCC heads contributed to the different strategic initiatives of DARIAH EU, developing related policy documents and improving procedures. All VCC heads mentored WG applications in the last year (see list of new WG's).

VCC Major Achievements and Activities

VCC1 heads held a number of coordinating virtual and face-to-face meetings, both between the main service providers DARIAH-DE and DARIAH-AT, as well as with the coordinators of the associated working groups. Especially to be highlighted a meeting in Vienna in February 2016 dedicated to discussing the broader perspective, mission and role of VCC1, as well as the shaping of the overall architecture of the research infrastructure, the portfolio of possible service offers and ways how to distribute the load of service provisioning among multiple partners. A related aspect was the administration and use of the namespace dariah.eu. It was decided that national subdomains will be introduced, like de.dariah.eu, at.dariah.eu, maintenance of which can be delegated to national technical coordinator in a technically clean manner (delegation of the DNS entries). Services deemed relevant for the overall infrastructure, can be promoted to general namespace: [\[service\].dariah.eu](http://[service].dariah.eu). A few such ser-

vices have been introduced, like tadirah.dariah.eu, vocabs.dariah.eu.

In the context of VCC1, DARIAH-DE provided a flexible development environment and sustainable production environment to simplify further development of the DH course registry. Also the discussion of migration of the service to the Austrian partner was initialized (to be completed in 2017). Furthermore DARIAH-DE offered sustainable hosting solution for the outcomes of the affiliated finished project CENDARI. Another line of action was informal exchange with the technical team of CLARIN on experiences in running technical infrastructure services as well as looking for synergies in the provisioning of the technical infrastructure. A specific example of shared work is the DH course registry, where plans for collaborative development and curation were formulated in 2016 and successfully implemented in 2017.

VCC1 also initiated or supported creation of new WGs.

WG Defining Cloud Infrastructure Services for DH, aimed at establishing liaison with EGI in the context of the project EGI-ENGAGE. Preliminary results of this WG were presented at numerous occasions, e.g. during the EGI conference in April 2016.

WG FIM4D (Federated Identity Management for DARIAH) a WG dedicated to the maintenance of the federated Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure and to its adoption among the service providers, with the aim to offer to the users Single-Sign-On capabilities for the DARIAH services. A workshop on this topic was organised by the WG in cooperation with the VCC.

VCC2 members contributed substantively to the re-organisation of the JRC in 2016, harnessing their large and active DARIAH community. Another focus was sustainability, which is a key quality indicator for DARIAH Services being offered beyond DARIAH communities, enhancing both scope and impact as targeted in projects, such as DARIAH HaS and DARIAH DESIR. Good and stable communication of such

services for research and education is the focus of DARIAH WG Community Engagement, which passed into new leadership, creating news and blogposts for a broader community of Arts and Humanities scholars and educators engaged with the digital transformation. It is also important to point out the changes that took place among the two main activities within the WG Education and Training: Course Registry and #dariahTeach. Despite having been accepted in 2017 as individual WGs, the process for their creation as individual WGs started already in 2016.

VCC3 was active in guiding the application process of new WGs (in particular Thesaurus Maintenance, Women Writers in History and Digital Numismatic). Furthermore, the VCC3 sought connections with the PARTHENOS project – among others, by setting up a dialogue with PARTHENOS management team in order to evaluate the DARIAH participation in PARTHENOS. VCC3 also established links with the project Humanities at Scale especially through the contribution to WP5, which is reshaping the in-kind contribution process to DARIAH, and to the open platform for academic publications being developed

in WP7. The VCC3 Head also acted as liaison with CLARIN ERIC, and functioned temporarily also as French National Coordinator. For what concerns the main objectives, VCC3 fine-tuned its own goals: among others, it promoted the use of standards in infrastructures and research services, it integrated work done by the projects ISIDORE and NARCIS into the VCC, and sought connection with research data registries and the work done by VCC1.

VCC4's main focus involves background research into the question of how to describe and measure impact of the use of digital infrastructures in humanities research. This work was strongly supported by DARIAH-DE. Taking into account the fact that humanities research is normally not done in large scale and formal collaborations comparable to the natural sciences, but rather in small groups and by individual researchers, impact cannot be measured by single large numbers. Instead, its measurement has to go beyond simple quantitative indicators and has to include qualitative change. To open up the discussion about these impact factors, the corresponding VCC4 Working Group extended its work on assessment (see below).

Working Group Snapshots

WG Impact factors and success criteria (VCC4)

In 2016 the working group Impact Factors and Success Criteria worked on expanding the Impactomatrix which is available at: <https://dariah-de.github.io/Impactomatrix/>. The Impactomatrix gathers potential impact factors and success criteria for assessing projects and research infrastructures (RI) in the arts and humanities. Based on a selection of 21 impact areas, corresponding factors, which influence change in these areas, are listed. Additionally, criteria are available which measure changes in the selected impact area. Digital research environments in the arts and humanities have to deal with the question of what value they provide for the scientific community and how they should make the best use of their granted money. For digital tools and infrastructure components in the Digital Humani-

ties, it is essential to define how they are impacting research practices in the Humanities and beyond. The impactomatrix helps to understand these implications with the goal to increase visibility and transparency of RIs, communicate their benefits to potential researchers and funding agencies and strengthen the influence of digital research in the Humanities.

Additionally, the working group added scope notes to the 21 impact areas as well as the references that were used to create the Impactomatrix (<https://github.com/DARIAH-DE/Impactomatrix/blob/master/Bibliography.md>)

The work was further presented at the DARIAH.EU Annual Meeting 2016 in Ghent.

WG Training and Education (VCC2)

Training and education are very important in DARIAH, and the Training and Education Working Group pursued two main activities in 2016: #dariahTeach and the DH registry.

Regarding #dariahTeach, the Erasmus+ partners worked on the continued development of the web portal, often giving talks and presenting posters (see www.dariah.eu/teach for the news). The team met three times during the year, in: Vienna, Athens and Maynooth. The group was responsible for developing the main sections of the courses and workshops, devoting particular attention to the design and the conceptualisation of the platform as

well as their impacts on teaching. Constant efforts were required to be ready on time for the launch of the platform in March 2017 in Lausanne (CH). The Dariah DH Registry has continued to expand its list of courses and curricula, and the Working Group is grateful to Hendrik Schmeer for his excellent work updating the software. The year 2016 was an important period of discussion in order to secure the sustainability of the registry, leading to a 2017 collaboration with CLARIN. Current discussions are open to expanding it beyond European frontiers, most notably with the French-speaking association Humanistica.

WG Sustainable Publishing of (Meta)data (VCC3)

The Working Group on Sustainable Publishing of (Meta)data is one of the youngest within DARIAH, being operational since October 2016 only. The WG's main goal, established by its members during the Annual Meeting in Ghent, is to offer a professional platform where archival holding institutes, research centers and e-science specialists can exchange information on existing projects and demonstrate good practices regarding the sustainable publishing of metadata. Since many such projects are already being initiated outside DARIAH, the WG does not aspire to develop new tools but rather to establish a meeting place where both members and non-members can exchange thoughts and discover inspirational projects.

Via regular skype meetings and a gathering at the DARIAH Annual Meeting, the WG on Sustainable Publishing of (Meta)data strives to support established institutes, but also to connect with partners such as EHRI and PARTHENOS. Both members and non-members are invited to present projects – such as Archives Portal Europe (APEX), MADDLAIN and MINT at the 2016 meeting – so other institutes can learn from these case studies and become motivated to actively participate in such initiatives as well.

The WG also aspires to create a more sustainable tool to share information on existing projects with members and non-members, and is currently discussing the best method to do so. The initial idea of creating a roadmap for institutes to identify their strengths and weaknesses and to determine which strategy to implement to improve their metadata has evolved in the direction of a blog or a website (under the DARIAH banner) to present existing projects. Via the site, information and inspirational publications will be offered, such as the WG's HAL-repository (consultable via <https://hal.inria.fr/hal-01281442v1/document>) which is currently being translated into French. In 2017, the WG aspires to produce a workable idea for creating a practical information hotspot.

The National Archives of Belgium, the International Institute of Social History, and Kazerne Dossin – Memorial, Museum and Documentation Centre on Holocaust and Human Rights are the WG's coordinating representatives. In 2016, its members included Trinity College Dublin, the Data Archiving and Networked Services (DANS), the Academy of Athens, INRIA and NIOD. A complete list of members and affiliated projects can be found on the WG page on the DARIAH wiki.

As we have seen, in addition to the projects we lead, Humanities at Scale and DESIR, DARIAH takes part in a number of European funded projects of relevance to its mission. In addition, in 2016 DARIAH participated in three Horizon 2020 proposals selected for funding by the European Commission (DESIR, HIRMEOS, E-RIHS PP) and officially joined the PARTHENOS project. We are also regularly engaged in cooperation with other ERICs as well as seek to broadcast the work we do to new audiences, which this year also gave us the opportunity to recast the yearly meeting into a more open forum for the exchange of ideas across the network and to the community of researchers beyond DARIAH.

DARIAH Projects

The Humanities at Scale Project

The project Humanities at Scale officially started in September 2015. The project is dedicated to enhancing the DARIAH-ERIC. It focuses on delivering a stronger core for DARIAH's operations as well as on providing more resources for all communities within DARIAH. This project will add essential services to DARIAH by enhancing its user community and with a wide range of innovation and training activities.

As project coordinator, DARIAH is heavily involved in all aspects of the projects. Tasks will range from growing the DARIAH community by creating hubs in regions not yet part of DARIAH, training activities, workshops and an Ambassadors programme, developing core services, such as a new model for making national contributions more accessible, collaborative platforms, a Data Deposit Recommendation Service, a metablog for Open Humanities Methods review.

To this end, a series of meetings was organised in 2016 to structure the work within the Consortium (in The Hague, Göttingen, and Ghent) and first training activities, notably a Winter School in Prague, and a workshop related to *Sustainable access to digital cultural and scientific heritage* that took place in Zagreb in June 2016. The Consortium requested and received an extension of 4 months and the project will officially end in December 2017.

FACTSHEET

FULL PROJECT NAME: Humanities at Scale: Evolving the DARIAH-ERIC

DURATION: 2 years, 3 months, from September 2015 to December 2017

CONSORTIUM: DARIAH-ERIC (project coordinator), CNRS, DANS, University of Göttingen, CNR, Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe, Academy of Athens, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Maynooth University, University of Aarhus, Institute of Ethnology and Folklore, Fachhochschule Potsdam.

EU CONTRIBUTION: EUR 1 930 139

CALL FOR PROPOSAL: H2020-INFRADEV-1-2015-1 – HORIZON 2020

WEBSITE: <http://has.dariah.eu/>

A first HaS Event: DARIAH Winter School in Prague

During the last week of October 2016, the DARIAH Winter School "Open Data Citation for Social Sciences and Humanities" was held in Prague.

This Winter School was conceived of as a collaborative event involving several institutions, speakers from different landscapes and participants with various backgrounds, working on the issues raised by the question of Open Data Citation for Social Sciences and Humanities. The objectives were to learn and exchange, to develop knowledge and skills, to prepare for further projects and finally to provide a great opportunity to gather different stakeholders during a full week.

20 participants from 16 countries were selected, reflecting a good balance between students (PhDs and academics in DH and SHS) and professionals (archive, scholarly communication, libraries, project management, edition). Speakers also participated during the week, adding a great source of animation and discussion.

The Winter School was organised around 10 thematic sessions which included Data Management

DESIR

The DESIR project sets out to strengthen the sustainability of DARIAH and firmly establish it as a long-term leader and partner within arts and humanities communities. By DESIR's definition, sustainability is an evolving 6-dimensional process, divided into the following challenges:

Dissemination: DESIR will organise a series dissemination events, including workshops in the US and Australia, to promote DARIAH tools and services and initiative collaborations.

Growth: DESIR sets out to prepare the ground for establishing DARIAH membership in six new countries: the UK, Finland, Spain, Switzerland, Czech Republic and Israel.

Technology: DESIR will widen the DARIAH research infrastructure in three areas, vital for DARIAH's long-term sustainability: entity-based search, scholarly content management, visualization and text analytic services.

Robustness: DESIR will make DARIAH's organizational structure and governance fit for the future and develop a detailed business plan and marketing strategy.

Trust: DESIR will measure the acceptance of DARIAH, especially in new communities, and define mechanisms to support trust and confidence in DARIAH.

Plan, Persistent Identification, Evaluation, Data journals, Social Impact, Open Access and Open Data Publication.

A full synthesis of the event: <http://opendatacite.huma-num.fr/>

Interviews: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=UUaWHmhqO2k>

Education: Through training and teaching DESIR will promote the use of DARIAH tools and services.

The project is coordinated by DARIAH which leads a Consortium of 15 partners from 12 countries, and is due to commence three years of work in January 2017.

FACTSHEET

FULL PROJECT NAME: DARIAH ERIC Sustainability Refined

DURATION: 3 years, from January 2017 to December 2019

CONSORTIUM: DARIAH-ERIC (project coordinator), University of Göttingen, University of Ghent, University of Warsaw, Universidade Nova de Lisboa, Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities, University of Hannover, INRIA, King's College London, University of Glasgow, Library of the Academy of Sciences of the Czech Republic, University of Helsinki, Swiss Institute of Bioinformatics, UNED, University of Haifa.

EU CONTRIBUTION: EUR 2 717 320

CALL FOR PROPOSAL: H2020-INFRADEV-2016-1 – HORIZON 2020

WEBSITE: www.dariah.eu

Affiliated projects

PARTHENOS

PARTHENOS
Pooling Activities, Resources and Tools
for Heritage E-research Networking,
Optimization and Synergies

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	Pooling Activities, Resources, and Tools for Heritage E-research Networking, Optimization and Synergies.
DURATION	4 years, from May 2015 to April 2019
CONSORTIUM	PIN scrI (project coordinator), KNAW, CNRS (Huma-Num), King’s College London, Fachhochschule Postdam, INRIA, Trinity College Dublin, CSIC, Austrian Academy of Sciences, SISMEL, CLARIN, CNR, FORTH, MIBACT-ICC, Academy of Athens, DARIAH-ERIC.
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 11 999 711
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-INFRADEV-1-2014-1 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://www.parthenos-project.eu/

ACTIVITIES

PARTHENOS is a Horizon 2020 project that aims at strengthening the cohesion of research in the broad sector of humanities, cultural heritage, history, archaeology and related fields through a thematic cluster of European Research Infrastructures, integrating initiatives, e-infrastructures and other world-class infrastructures, building bridges between different, although closely related, fields. It will achieve this objective through the definition and support of common standards, the coordination of joint activities, the harmonization of policy definition and implementation, and the development of pooled services and of shared solutions to common problems. Also, PARTHENOS supports the work of the two main research infrastructures, DARIAH and CLARIN, and as well as various integration projects addressing cultural domains, such as ARIADNE, CENDARI and EHRI.

DARIAH joined the PARTHENOS consortium officially in November 2016.

HIRMEOS

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure
DURATION	30 months, from January 2017 to June 2019
CONSORTIUM	CNRS (project coordinator), National Hellenic Research Foundation, OAPEN, Max Weber Stiftung, University of Göttingen, Ubiquity Press, Open Book Publishers, DARIAH ERIC, University of Turin.
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 1 997 878,13
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-EINFRA-2016-1 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://www.hirmeos.eu/

ACTIVITIES

The project HIRMEOS (High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure) will improve five important publishing platforms for the open access monographs in the SSH and enhance their technical capacities and services, rendering technologies and content interoperable and embedding them fully into the European Open Science Cloud. HIRMEOS will prototype innovative services for monographs in view of full integration in the European Open Science Cloud by providing additional data, links and interactions to the documents, paving the way to new potential tools for research assessment, which is still a major challenge in the SSH. The platforms participating (OpenEdition Books, OAPEN Library, EKT Open Book Press, Ubiquity Press and Göttingen University Press) will be enriched with tools that enable identification, authentication and interoperability (DOI, ORCID, Fundref), and tools that enrich information and entity extraction (INRIA (N)ERD), the ability to annotate monographs (Hypothes.is), and gather usage and alternative metric data.

relationship with INRIA and leads WP3 “Entities Recognition Services”, as well as participating in the WP7 “Community outreach and Exploitation”.

The HIRMEOS project will also start start in January 2017. DARIAH participates to HIRMEOS in a close

E-RIHS PP

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	High Integration of Research Monographs in the European Open Science infrastructure
DURATION	3 years, from February 2017 to January 2020
CONSORTIUM	CNR (project coordinator), Royal Institute for Cultural Heritage, The Cyprus Institute, The Institute of Theoretical and Applied Mechanics, German Archaeological Institute, CSIC, CENIEH, CNRS, DARIAH-ERIC, FORTH, Hungarian Academy of Sciences, The Discovery Programme: Centre for Archaeology and Innovation Ireland, Israel Antiquities Authority, CERIC-ERIC, PIN srl, Ministry of Education, Culture and Science (Netherlands), Nicolaus Copernicus University in Toruń, Laboratório Nacional de Engenharia Civil, Javni zavod republike Slovenije za varstvo kulturne dediščine, University College London.
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 3 999 449
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-EU.1.4.1.1. – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://cordis.europa.eu/project/rcn/209507_en.html

ACTIVITIES

E-RIHS PP is a coordination and support action addressing the topic “Preparatory Phase and support to early phase of ESFRI projects” within the call H2020-INFRADEV-02-2016. The specific action addressed by this project is the preparation of E-RIHS, the European Research Infrastructure for Heritage Science (HS), one of the six new projects which entered the ESFRI Roadmap in 2016, and the only research infrastructure project in the Social and Cultural Innovation section of the Roadmap.

E-RIHS will help the preservation of the World’s Heritage by enabling cutting-edge research in heritage science, liaising with governments and heritage institutions to promote its constant development and, finally, raising the appreciation of the large public for cultural and natural heritage and the recognition of its historic, social and economic significance.

E-RIHS PP will start in 2017 and will last three years (2017-2020). The first two will be used to address governance, financial aspects, legal documents and logistics. This will lead to a business plan ready for application to ERIC, or to another suitable legal form, by 2019. The last year will be devoted to negotiations with stakeholders, based on the agreed instruments, further strategic planning and to start up of activities for entering the transition phase. E-RIHS will hopefully be launched as a stand-alone RI in 2021.

DARIAH will lead the task 3.2 “Human Resources Strategic Planning”, drawing together a report which will explore and analyse different Human Resources scenarios for E-RIHS, including the type of expertise and skills required, develop strategies for creating engagement and support career building.

RITrain

FACTSHEET	
FULL PROJECT NAME	Research Infrastructures Training Programme
DURATION	4 years, from September 2015 to August 2019
CONSORTIUM	BBMRI-ERIC (project coordinator), EMBL-EBI, Medical University of Vienna, INFRAFRONTIER GMBH, EATRIS,-ERIC, ECRIN-ERIC, Universidade do Minho, Institute of Molecular Genetics, Imperial College, University of Milano-Bicocca, CNRS, SHARE-ERIC
EU CONTRIBUTION	EUR 1 995 633,75
CALL FOR PROPOSAL	H2020-INFRA supp-2014-2 – HORIZON 2020
WEBSITE	http://ritrain.eu/home

ACTIVITIES

The RITrain project was developed due to the increasing demand for skilled managers in Research Infrastructures (RIs) and to create a corresponding pilot curriculum for an Executive Masters in RI management. The first step was the definition of a universal organisational competency framework, followed by mapping relevant existing courses, so that a thoroughgoing gap analysis could be performed, which in turn informed the content and thrust of the innovative Executive Masters programme now being offered. Through additional webinars and staff exchanges accompanied by regular face-to-face sessions, RITrain's aim is to contribute significantly in the field to the continuous professional development of current and future generations of RI managers.

DARIAH has a particular interest as a partner in RITrain for various reasons. First, this is where on-the-job experience and best practice can be shared thanks to the extensive RITrain network, through which it operates an open staff exchange scheme. Secondly, DARIAH is committed to creating a long-term framework for an adaptive business model re-

gime. For the overall longevity and thus viability of the research infrastructure consortium paradigm it is particularly important to focus on skilling a cohort of managers that can also itself train future staff, in light of DARIAH's mandate to continue to bring about further digital transformation in the arts and humanities until 2035. Finally, RITrain contributes to highlighting the role of DARIAH as one of the main research infrastructure in humanities. Indeed, two of its directors, Jennifer Edmond and Laurent Romary, have been involved in specific RITrain webinars to share their insights on the impact of successful research infrastructures on arts and humanities research.

DARIAH's work with RITrain has been led for the DARIAH Coordination Office in 2016 by Suzanne Dumouchel and Francesca Morselli.

DARIAH Outreach

Promoting Research in Europe: An Inter-ERIC Communications Initiative

The dissemination of DARIAH's results, making them available for all researchers, and getting potential new users involved, is designed to further and complement the building and organising of DARIAH's core services and activities.

In that light, a collaboration in terms of communications with the current four ERICs in the SSH field (CLARIN, DARIAH, ESS, SHARE), as well as the ESFRI Landmark CESSDA, was established this year in order to create synergies and draw on mutual strengths. In addition, PARTHENOS, which supports the work of CLARIN and DARIAH, as well as CLARIAH, a national counterpart to CLARIN and DARIAH in the Netherlands, which is directly and deeply embedded

in the Europe-wide ESFRI enterprise, were brought on board as an important part of this initiative.

Communications staff from each of these contributors have started working together on a draft plan for joint communication activities and have regular virtual meetings. Shared news stories as well as a dedicated Twitter are planned to become available from January 2017 as well as an informative webpage about those involved in the collaboration.

In this way, the Inter-ERIC network seeks to reinforce our collective aim – the innovative and long-term support of new and sustainable ways of conducting research.

Making research accessible: The DARIAH Theme 2016, “Public Humanities”

The DARIAH Theme is a series of activities and events related to an annual thematic priority set by the Board of Directors. For our second theme for 2016, we have selected ‘Public Humanities’. The first theme in 2015 was ‘Open Humanities’.

The DARIAH infrastructure is not only a network but also a platform to bring digital arts and humanities initiatives in Europe together using open standards and policies. The high level goal of DARIAH is to enable this platform to launch digital humanities in all regions of the European Research Area. A cornerstone of our work is to help Members to establish best practices on how to start and foster their own digital arts and humanities research. We are committed to support any digitally non-mature research and establish links to the shared DARIAH body of knowledge.

The theme for 2016 targeted the platform impact of DARIAH's work on the public. We define ‘Public Humanities’ as the activities of any cultural institution that engages the public with Arts and Humanities

research and thus adds to the public's well-being. The public either refers to the general public or special organisations such as media or educational institutions, such as schools.

To further develop its work with the public, DARIAH will run a conference in 2017 that will investigate public value-creation in the creative and cultural industries through the digital transformation from a European perspective. We will make use of the fact that in 2017 Aarhus, the coordinator of the Danish national DARIAH project, will be the European Capital of Culture. The winners of this call, seven in all, will present the results of their work at this conference.

As an open infrastructure, DARIAH is committed to making research more accessible to the general public and demonstrate the continued importance of arts and humanities work for the cultural, social and political life in Europe. The Humanities, and the understanding and skills involved.

Towards a scientific conference: The first DARIAH Annual Event

The DARIAH-EU Annual Event builds on the previous General Virtual Competency Centre meetings. In 2016 DARIAH decided to evolve and open up these internal meetings. As a result the first DARIAH-EU Annual Event took place in October in Ghent.

The DARIAH Annual Event is not only designed to assist our working groups but is also open to researchers beyond the DARIAH community. It features a series of engaging keynote lectures and interactive sessions, which bring together researchers, technologists, data scientists and cultural heritage professionals. Additionally the DARIAH Annual Event enables colleagues to work together face-to-face on their DARIAH activities, e.g. in Working Group meetings.

During the meeting there were updates from the DARIAH-EU team, including a “Towards a DARIAH Strategic Plan” workshop, where ideas around the development of a data reuse charter were discussed. Tuesday morning was dedicated to the DARIAH-EU Working Group activities including lightning talks and a working group marketplace.

Additionally the event featured a Digital Arts and Humanities Lab. This interactive session brought together researchers, technologists, data scientists and cultural heritage professionals, to demonstrate and engage with data, tools and services around the theme of Open and Public Humanities.

A visual recap of the event can be found on the DARIAH-EU Youtube channel: <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ptoKODTjqUw>

Who's who in DARIAH and who's new?

Organisational overview

Interactions as described in Statutes and IRP

New Board members

According to its statutes the DARIAH-ERIC has three part-time directors. Together they are responsible for the day-to-day operations of DARIAH. In doing this, they consult with the Senior Management Team and are supported by the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office.

During the summer of 2016 Conny Kristel and Tobias Blanke announced they would both leave DARIAH's Board of Directors by the end of the year. Following a decision of the 5th General Assembly (GA) meeting in May 2016, a call of applications was issued and a committee was formed to select two appropriate names among the candidates, prepar-

ing their formal appointment by the 6th GA meeting in November 2016.

The two candidates proposed by the selection committee were Jennifer Edmond and Frank Fischer. The Chair of DARIAH's General Assembly, Jacques Dubucs, who was also part of the committee, described the selection process as inspiring and said, "we had many applications, and they were all ranging from very good to outstanding. Finally two exceptionally good candidates were picked", Jacques concluded. In its November 2016 meeting the consortium's General Assembly (GA) approved the nominations.

Jennifer Edmond

Dr Jennifer Edmond is the Director of Strategic Projects for the Faculty of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences at Trinity College Dublin and the co-director of the Trinity Center for Digital Humanities. She holds a PhD in Germanic Languages and Literatures from Yale University, and applies her training as a scholar of language, narrative and culture to the study and promotion of advanced methods in and infrastructures for the humanities.

In this vein, she has developed a significant profile in European research and research policy circles in the past 5 years, having been named one of Ireland's five "Champions of EU Research" in 2012. She coordinated the €6.5m CENDARI FP7 (2012-1026) project and is a partner in the related infrastructure cluster, PARTHENOS. Her other EU projects have included coordinating Researcher Night in 2013, Europeana Cloud the ESF Network NeDiMAH and

Interview with Jennifer Edmond: How DARIAH Helps Develop an Open Science Policy for Europe

Jennifer, since the end of May you are a member of the Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP). Please tell us, how exactly does your work in the OSPP look like?

The OSPP is a small, high-level group of experts representing stakeholder perspectives relevant for the development of Open Science policy. We are charged with the mission to consult with the Commission and our stakeholder groups, and to shape policy responses to the wide range of issues associated with Open Science.

Why is an open science policy so important for Europe?

Open Science is one of the three guiding principles recently announced by the European Commission as mechanisms to strengthen Europe's competitiveness in science across the disciplines. By sharing results and resources early, widely and more fluidly, Europe's research system can become not only more efficient, but deeper, more insightful.

How is your role in DARIAH connected to your nomination as a member of the OSPP?

Each member of the OSPP represents the interests of a particular organisation or consortium: in my case that organisation is DARIAH. I think it speaks well for the potential reach and impact of the OSPP that they include not only the large and established players in the research ecosys-

tem, like the universities and the publishers, but also the so-called intermediaries, representing emerging practices and interests, like DARIAH.

How do you think will DARIAH profit from your engagement in the OSPP?

I worry that current trends in the development of Open Science policy are based upon very science-focussed conceptions of research process, research data, research careers, etc. Through DARIAH's inclusion among the represented organisations, we can bring the humanities perspective as well. This can help DARIAH to keep its own policies at the leading edge within Europe, but also to fulfil its role as a source of support and expertise for the humanities research community.

If you are looking at the upcoming work in the OSPP, what are the biggest challenges?

It's a huge mandate, encompassing the full research process, from citizen science and alt-metrics to publishing and research data sharing. Some of the tools and norms needed to realise good practice in these areas are yet to be established: in other cases, significant vested interests may stand in the way of balanced development. It certainly won't be an easy task, but the stakes for the European researcher are high.

Thank you very much, Jennifer.

the forthcoming ICT 'sister project' Knowledge Complexity (KPLEX).

Jennifer represents DARIAH in the Open Science Policy Platform (OSPP), where she supports the European Commission in developing an Open Science Policy (cp. Interview below).

Jennifer has also played a leadership role in numerous strategic developments at national and institutional level, including the creation of Yale's McDougal Graduate Centre, the University of Nottingham's 2005 revisioning of its graduate services provision, and, in Ireland, the foundation of the 'Texts, Contexts, Cultures' graduate training programme, the Digital Humanities Observatory and the Trinity Long Room Hub research institute. She has lent her expertise in the development of infrastructure to a wide variety of initiatives and agencies, from the food manufacturing industry through to the Korean national maritime agency, and is a strong proponent of public outreach for academic research, having presented her work to general audiences, live as well as through radio, television and video, including through the medium of stand up comedy.

Frank Fischer

Frank Fischer is Associate Professor for Digital Humanities at the National Research University Higher School of Economics in Moscow. He studied Computer Science, German Literature, and Spanish Philology at the University of Leipzig and at Middlesex University, London, and is an Ancien Pensionnaire de l'École Normale Supérieure in Paris.

Frank received his PhD from the University of Jena for his study on the dramatic works of Joachim Wilhelm von Brawe and their contemporary translations into Russian, Danish, and French. As a student, he worked as a programmer for the Deutscher Wortschatz project and for TextTech, a company specialised in text mining.

After graduating, he was an editor for the Brockhaus encyclopedia and researcher at the Leipzig University Library. From 2013 to 2016 he was coordinator of the Göttingen Centre for Digital Humanities and staff member of DARIAH-DE. He co-founded a working group on the network analysis of literary texts (<http://lina.digital/>) and the Digital Humanities research blog weltliteratur.net (<http://weltliteratur.net/>).

National Coordinators Committee (NCC)

During its meeting in November 2016 Toma Tasovac expressed his willingness to succeed Charly Moerth as Chair of the NCC. He furthermore proposed Sally Chambers as Vice-Chair. The NCC unanimously voted for Toma Tasovac and Sally Chambers as Chair

and Vice-Chair of the NCC. They will started their work in January 2017. For a more detailed overview of the work and the evolvement of the NCC see Annex.

Senior Management Team (SMT)

The Board of Directors consults the SMT on all general matters. The SMT is composed of the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the National Coordinators Committee, as well as the Chair and Vice-Chair of

the Joint Research Committee. In addition the Chair of the Scientific Board and the relevant officers of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office are invited to attend Senior Management Team meetings.

Dariah Coordination Office (DCO)

The daily work of DARIAH-EU is undertaken by the DCO, it is responsible for finance, coordination and communications. By the end of 2016 it had eight members, including the Chief Integra-

tion Officer's Team (CIO Team). A comprehensive overview of the work of the CIO team is featured in the annex.

<p>Mike Mertens Chief Executive Officer</p>	<p>Mike is the primary representative of DARIAH-EU. He is responsible for the overall governance and coordination of DARIAH.</p>	
<p>Andrea Scharnhorst Chief Integration Officer</p>	<p>Andrea chairs DARIAH-EU's Joint Research Committee and coordinates the collection of national in-kind contributions to DARIAH-EU.</p>	
<p>Anne Grésillon Chief Organisation Officer</p>	<p>Anne manages the financial, administrative and legal activities of DARIAH-EU and supports the DARIAH Board of Directors in all related matters.</p>	

Francesca Morselli CIO-Team	Francesca helps coordinating the activities of DARIAH's Virtual Competence Centers (VCCs) and their related working groups.	
Marco Raciti European Project Manager	Marco Raciti is responsible for supporting and managing national and European external funding for the DARIAH ERIC.	
Suzanne Dumouchel Programme Implementation Officer	Suzanne's focus is on working with new and established digitally-enabled arts and humanities researcher communities.	
Arnaud Roi Finance Officer	Arnaud is in charge of all financial matters related to DARIAH-EU activities.	
Jakob Epler Communications Officer	Jakob manages DARIAH-EU's internal and external communications.	

Virtual Competence Centers (VCC)

DARIAH's VCCs have also seen some changes in personnel in 2016. The list below gives an overview.

VCC1: Eveline Wandl-Vogt (ACDH-OEAW, Austria)(outgoing); Matej Durco (ACDH-OEAW, Austria) (incoming) and Tibor Kálmán (GWDG, Germany)

VCC2: Susan Schreibman (Maynooth University) (outgoing); Jennifer Edmond (Trinity College Dublin, Ireland) (Incoming) and Marianne Ping Huang (Aarhus University, Denmark)

VCC3: Nicolas Larrousse (HumaNum, France); Andrea Scharnhorst (DANS-KNAW, The Netherlands) (outgoing) – Marcin Werla (Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center) (incoming)

VCC4: Dirk Wintergrün (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science, Germany); Hansmichael Hohenegger (CNR) (outgoing); Fabio Ciotti (Universita' Tor Vergata, Italy) (incoming)

New Working Groups

Defining Cloud Infrastructure Services for DH

WG Chairs: (Eveleine Wandl Volgt, ACDH_OeAW; Tibor Kálmán, GWDG; Rene van Horik DANS-KNAW, NL)

This working group will explore the offers of EGI and the needs of DARIAH. The outcome will be an answer to the question: 'how can VCC1 be a broker between cloud provider and humanities? In particular the project will focus on: defining the needs of the digital humanities and giving an overview of the building blocks that EGI can provide; connecting DARIAH and EGI authentication infrastructure; and experimenting, by building demonstrators of repository services and information retrieval services.

WG FIM4D (Federated Identity Management for DARIAH)

WG Chair: Peter Giets, (DAASI, Germany)

Within DARIAH-DE, an Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure has been set up that allows for any researcher to seamlessly authenticate to DARIAH services with the password of their home institution. This working group aims at disseminating information about this infrastructure and will set up a number of pilots to integrate services from different DARIAH countries into this infrastructure.

WG CENDARI Sustain

WG Chair: Jennifer Edmond, Trinity College Dublin, Ireland

The CENDARI SUSTAIN working group seeks to support the development of DARIAH by continuing to investigate how DARIAH can contribute to the sustainability of the research infrastructure developed during the CENDARI project, and to broaden the application of such investigation to other research infrastructures in the DARIAH landscape.

WG Women Writers in History (WWIH)

WG Chairs: Suzan van Dijk, Huygens-ING, The Netherlands and Amelia Sanz, Universidad Complutense Madrid, Spain)

Large-scale sources (such as periodicals, inventories of libraries, private correspondences of authors) containing data about the contemporary reception and impact of women writers' activities, have begun to be available online, and they also start leading to a new perspective on women's place in literary history (and in society...). DARIAH-WWIH plans to continue and reinforce the activities of the NEWW (New approaches to European Women's Writing), COST-WWIH and HERA TTT members, enlarging the network by inviting also other colleagues and users of the NEWW Virtual Research Environment. The working group will also encourage initiatives for crowdsourcing and citizen's participation in the field of women's literary history. Finally, it will maintain contact with members of other institutions in women's cultural heritage and relevant networks

WG Sustainable Publishing of (Meta)data

WG Chairs: Dorien Styven (Kazerne Dossin, Belgium), Johan Van der Eycken (ARA, Belgium), Afelonne Doek (IISH, The Netherlands), Eric de Ruijter (IISH, The Netherlands)

Too often, metadata are created in bespoke systems by collection-holding institutions for internal use only and are not published in a machine-usable form to the outside digital world. This working group wishes to offer a platform for archivists to reflect on their methodologies to ensure sustainable publishing and sharing of their metadata and data. As such, this project finds itself in the heart of DARIAH's mission to ensure that accepted standards and best practice examples are followed. It is the mission of this working group to help ensuring the description and availability of Europe's heritage in an interoperable way and with the highest possible quality and future utility.

Administrative, legal and regulatory

- Legal basis of existence
- What an ERIC is for/what a Research Infrastructure is for

European Research Infrastructure Consortium

The community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC) is a specific legal form to facilitate the establishment and operation of research infrastructures with European interest. The Commission provides practical guidelines to help potential applicants.

The principal task of ERIC is to establish and operate new or existing research infrastructures on a non-economic basis. The ERIC becomes a legal entity from the date the Commission decision setting up the ERIC takes effect.

An ERIC can carry out some limited economic activities related to this task.

The ERIC legal framework provides:

- a European joint-venture (also allows the participation of non-European countries)
- a legal capacity recognised in all EU Member States
- flexibility to adapt to specific requirements of each infrastructure
- a faster process than creating an international organisation
- exemptions from VAT and excise duty"

(Quoted from https://ec.europa.eu/research/infrastructures/index_en.cfm?pg=eric)

The ERIC framework is underpinned by Council Regulation (EC) No 723/2009 of 25 June 2009 on the Community legal framework for a European Research Infrastructure Consortium (ERIC). See: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?qid=1464858763037&uri=CELEX:32009R0723>

Budget

Income and Expenditures

Balance 2015	494,466.00 €
Income DARIAH 2016	
Cash contributions 2016	666,513.00 €
Total income	666,513.00 €
Expenditures DARIAH 2016	
staff costs	408,982.40 €
DARIAH Theme	49,940.00 €
travel costs	39,073.16 €
communication costs	5,421.98 €
consumables	7,759.08 €
server support	3,272.50 €
bank charges	1,867.85 €
Total expenditures	516,316.97 €

Balance 2015	494,466 €
Total income 2016	666,513 €
Total expenditures 2016	516,317 €
Balance 2016	644,662 €

External Funding in 2016

DESIR

In 2016, DARIAH received 2.037.990€ from the EU Commission for the pre-financement of the EU-project DESIR. As coordinator of the project DARIAH is in charge of distributing the prefinancing among the partners. As a result, DARIAH distributed 1.730,090€ among its partners and kept 307,500€ for its part of the project.

EU-Project DESIR	307,500.00 €
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Project Europeana

Project Europeana	938.00 €
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External funding is solely used to carry out specific projects and are not part of DARIAH's income or expenditures.

Annex 1: Report of NCC Activities

Each DARIAH Member Country appoints a National Coordinator, who coordinates DARIAH activities in his or her country. In the National Coordinator Committee (NCC), they meet regularly to integrate their national DARIAH activities at the European level. As one of the operational bodies of the DARIAH-ERIC, the role of the NCC is to support the Board of Directors, in particular by producing a synthesis of the national DARIAH roadmaps and proposing the annual in-kind contributions of each Member.

To prepare the ground for their work in 2016, the NCC met in November 2015 at the Centre Marc Bloch, the seat of the DARIAH-EU Coordination Office in Berlin. One of the first items on the agenda for the election of a new Chair and Vice-Chair of the NCC, which, as outlined in the statutes, are elected for a term of 12 months. Prior to the initiation of the call for nominations, Luca Pezzati, National Coordinator for DARIAH-IT and current Vice-Chair of the NCC, communicated that he would be stepping down from his role in December 2015.

As outlined in the Internal Rules of Procedure, in October 2015, a call for nominations for a new Chair and Vice-Chair was launched. Marianne Backes, the National Coordinator of DARIAH in Luxembourg, was put forward as a candidate for the role of Chair of the NCC. As no further nominations for the role of Vice-Chair were received, the current Chair of the NCC, Karlheinz Mörth (DARIAH-AT), confirmed that he would be willing to continue to serve on the NCC as Vice-Chair.

During the NCC meeting in November 2015, Marianne Backes and Karlheinz Mörth were unanimously elected as the NCC Chair and Vice-Chair, from 1 January 2016. The NCC thanked both Luca Pezzati for his work as the previous Vice-Chair and Karlheinz Mörth for his willingness to contribute to the continuity of the NCC. With the new Chair and Vice-Chair in place, the NCC was ready for the year's activities ahead.

One of the major themes arising from discussions in the NCC meeting of November 2015 was on the

need to evolve the model of collecting, assessing and approving In-Kind Contributions. Following a detailed analysis of the national in-kind contributions that had been collected to date by Henk Harmsen, DARIAH-EU's Chief Integration Officer (CIO) and his team, it became clear that a more strategic approach to in-kind contributions was required. Furthermore, the need to distinguish between inventories of national digital humanities activities and concrete contributions to infrastructural services were identified. This initial analysis laid the foundations for the evaluation of the model of in-kind contributions to be carried out by Lisa De Leeuw (DANS) and colleagues, during 2016, as part of the Humanities at Scale (HaS) project.

During 2016, new communication structures for the NCC were established, including a migration to using Basecamp, provided centrally by DARIAH-EU, in order to streamline communications. Furthermore, the timing of NCC meetings, in relation to the meetings of the DARIAH General Assembly, was reviewed. With National Coordinators playing a key liaison role between the scientific community and the funding bodies, the importance of NCC meetings take place prior to the General Assembly was agreed.

The summer of 2016 bought a restructuring of the research landscape in Luxembourg, with the integration of the Centre Virtuel de la Connaissance sur l'Europe (CVCE) into the University of Luxembourg. This resulted in the need to appoint a new DARIAH National Coordinator for Luxembourg as well as Chair of the NCC. Karlheinz Mörth (DARIAH-AT), as Vice-Chair of the NCC and previous Chair, kindly offered to Chair the NCC for the remainder of 2016.

Due to the change in the leadership of the NCC and the frequency of meetings, the importance of revitalising the DARIAH-EU Senior Management Team (SMT), became clear. The SMT, composed of the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the National Coordinator Committee, and the Chair and the Vice-Chair of the Joint Research Committee, along with the attendance of the relevant officers of the DARI-

AH-EU Coordination Office (DCO) and the Chair of the Scientific Board, is a key team for contributing to managing the day-to-day activities of DARIAH. The role of the SMT is to act as sounding board for the Board of Directors, for all general matters related to the operation of DARIAH. As an election for a new Chair and Vice-Chair of the NCC was required during autumn of 2016, it was agreed that January 2017 would be an ideal time to reinstate the DARIAH SMT, by organising a number of 'DARIAH Strategy Days' in early 2017.

Furthermore, 2016 saw an important strategic impetus for the National Coordinator Committee through the success of the H2020 DARIAH-ERIC Sustainability Defined (DESIR) project proposal. Work Package 3 of the DESIR project focuses on 'Growth'. The main goal of the work package is to enlarge the DARIAH Membership to include six new members: the Czech Republic, Finland, Israel, Spain, Switzerland and the UK. Led by the University of Warsaw from DARIAH-Poland, one of the newest DARIAH Members, the intention of the work package is to provide support and guidance for these 'DARIAH Accession Countries' to become full members of DARIAH-EU, through the development of country-specific strategies and action plans. It was agreed that close cooperation between the 'DARIAH Accession Coordinators' as future National Coordinators and members of the NCC would be vital. By working closely with the current DARIAH National Coordinators, the possibility of sharing best practices and experiences would be facilitated, which would be extremely valuable for the accession process.

The final NCC meeting of the year took place in Vienna in November 2016. Again, the goal of this meeting was to prepare the action plan for the NCC for 2017, as well as appointing a new Chair and Vice-Chair. As for 2016, a call for nominations was launched prior to the November meeting. This time, two new candidates were put forward: Toma Tasovac (DARIAH-RS) for the Chair of the NCC, with Sally Chambers (DARIAH-BE) as Vice-Chair. Both candidates were unanimously elected during the

November 2016 meeting, for a term of office, starting from January 2017.

The face-to-face General Assembly meeting, which followed the NCC meeting in Vienna, laid the ground for the NCC activities for 2017. With the DARIAH construction phase approaching an end in August 2019, the General Assembly asked the NCC to gauge the willingness for DARIAH Founding Members to renew their Membership for a further 5 years, from 2019 onwards. While it was anticipated that formal commitment from countries could not be expected at this stage, the essential role of National Coordinators in advising their National Representatives regarding the renewal process, could be set in motion. The collection of indicatory information regarding: a) current status of DARIAH National Roadmaps, as well as the status of DARIAH in National ESFRI roadmaps[1], b) national sustainability plans for the provision of digital services for the humanities research community, c) national strategies concerning the engagement in research infrastructures in the humanities, d) whether closer coordination between humanities research infrastructures would be contemplated and e) initial indications as to the likelihood of countries extending their financial commitment to DARIAH beyond the initial term of contract, would be possible. Not only, would the answers to these questions be valuable in themselves, but would provide an excellent evidence base, for the developing of a synthesis of DARIAH National Roadmaps at the European level. The end of 2016, marked an exciting year of activity ahead for the NCC.

Annex 2: Report of Joint Research Committee and CIO-Team Activities

In 2016, the Joint Research Committee continued to meet regularly. Progress in the Working groups is a recurring topic, but also the preparation of the Annual DARIAH Event. In 2016, as we have seen, the Annual Meeting took on an expanded brief, and the host institution, represented by Sally Chambers, gave it a slightly different shape by introducing key lectures and a marketplace where all can demo services, next to keeping earlier successful elements as meeting space for WG's, projects, and DARIAH bodies. The CIO team and the JRC together have now a workflow for the content and organisational preparation of this event.

In 2016 the CIO team also prepared a detailed report of the state of the art of the WG for the General Assembly. One of the main outcomes from the

interviews was the call for more tangible support for the Working groups, which will be implemented by a new internal funding scheme for the working groups, in 2017.

Organizationally, in order to reinforce the role of the VCC heads and to guarantee sufficient time resources for them, the CIO team proposed and developed a Memorandum of Understanding. The MoU symbolizes the agreement between the institution to which the VCC head belongs to and the DARIAH ERIC. This document is considered an important milestone in the growth of the VCCs as strong bodies able to take part in the DARIAH's strategic developments in the years to come.

Table Staff in the VCCs and CIO Team

POSITION	CHANGES IN 2016	STATE (as of September 2017)
VCC1 Head		Tibor Kálmán (GWDG)
VCC1 Co-Head	Eveline Wandl-Volgt (ACDH-OEAW)	Matej Durco (ACDH-OEAW)
VCC 2 Head		Marianne Huang (University Aarhus)
VCC 2 Co-Head	Susan Schreibman (Maynooth University) -> Jennifer Edmond (TCD)	Agiatis Benardou (DCU)
VCC 3 Head		Nicolas Larrousse (Huma-Num)
VCC 3 Co-Head	Hella Hollander (DANS-KNAW) -> Andrea Scharnhorst (DANS-KNAW)	Marcin Werla (Poznań Supercomputing and Networking Center)
VCC 4 Head		Dirk Wintergrün (Max Planck Institute for the History of Science)
VCC 4 Co-Head	Hansmichael Hohenegger (CNR)	Fabio Ciotti (University Tor Vergata)
JRC Vice Chair	Sophie David (Huma-Num)	Tibor Kálmán (GWDG)
JRC Chair and CiO	Henk Harmsen (DANS-KNAW)	Andrea Scharnhorst (DANS-KNAW)
CIO team officer	Lisa de Leeuw (DANS-KNAW)	Francesca Morselli (DANS-KNAW)
CiO team officer		Femmy Admiraal (DANS-KNAW)
CiO team secretarial support		Ingrid van der Elst (DANS-KNAW)

Annex 3: List of National Representatives in 2016

COUNTRY	NAME	INSTITUTION
Austria	Ursula Brustmann	Federal Ministry of Science, Research and Economy
Belgium	Chris De Loof	Belgian Science Policy Office
Croatia	Stasa Skenzic	Ministry of Science, Education and Sport
Cyprus	Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus University of Technology
Denmark	Katinka Stenbjørn	Danish Agency for Science, Technology and Innovation – Ministry of Higher Education and Science
France	Jaques Dubucs	Ministère de l'Education nationale, de l'Enseignement supérieur et de la Recherche
Germany	Klaus Schindel	Federal Ministry of Education and Research
Greece	Helen Katsiadakis	Academy of Athens
Ireland	Eucharia Meehan	Irish Research Council
Italy	Lino Leonardi	National Research Council of Italy
Luxembourg	Robert Kerger	Ministry for Higher Education and Research
Malta	Milena Dobрева	Malta Libraries Council
Netherlands	Alice Dijkstra	Netherlands Organisation for Scientific Research
Poland	Dariusz Drewniak	Ministry of Science and Higher Education
Portugal	Daniel Carapau	FCT – Foundation for Science & Technology
Serbia	Tamara Butigan-Vučaj	National Library of Serbia
Slovenia	Albin Kralj	Ministry of Education, Science and Sport

Annex 4: List of National Coordinators in 2016

COUNTRY	NAME	INSTITUTION
Austria	Charly Moerth	Austrian Academy of Sciences
Belgium	Christophe Verbruggen	University of Ghent
Croatia	Koraljka Kuzman Slogar	Institute of Ethnology and Folklore Research
Cyprus	Marinos Ioannides	Cyprus University of Technology
Denmark	Birte Christensen-Dalsgaard	DIGHUMLAB – DK
France	Olivier Baude	Huma-Num (CNRS)
Germany	Heike Neuroth	University of Göttingen
Greece	Helen Katsiadakis	Academy of Athens
Ireland	Susan Schreibman	National University of Ireland Maynooth
Italy	Emiliano Degl’Innocenti	National Research Council of Italy
Luxembourg	Andreas Fickers	Centre for Contemporary and Digital History
Malta	Milena Dobрева	Malta Libraries Council
Netherlands	Henk Wals	International Institute of Social History
Poland	Jakub Szprot	University of Warsaw
Portugal	Amélia Aguiar de Andrade	Infrastructure ROSSIO
Serbia	Toma Tasovac	Belgrade Center for Digital Humanities
Slovenia	Jurij Hadalin	Institute of Contemporary History

Annex 5: List of DARIAH related publications

An inventory of 818 publications has been created based on the identification in Google Scholar of all documents making reference to DARIAH. The followed bibliography concerns the restrictive period between 2016 and 2017, resulting in a total of 148 publications. It covers both traditional publications (journal article, conferences, workshops) and other types of communication (oral presentations, videos, newsletters).

The number of publications is constantly increasing, demonstrating both the dynamism of the research infrastructure and the communities in terms of the fields and of geographical areas it covers

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